

Formulation And Evaluation of Antiarthritis Tablet

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ABSTRACT

Medicinal plants are widely used in traditional Indian society. *Enicostema axillare* particularly its extract demonstrate anti arthritic activity by reducing inflammation and pain associated with arthritis. The present study focuses on the formulation and evaluation of anti-arthritis tablets aimed at providing effective relief from arthritic symptoms with improved patient compliance. Formula were prepared using the direct compression method with selected anti-arthritic agents along with suitable excipients, binders, and disintegrants.

Keywords: *Enicostema axillare*, Anti-arthritic activity, arthritis, patient compliance, binders.

INTRODUCTION

Antiarthritis: Arthritis is a chronic inflammatory disorder affecting joints, characterized by pain, stiffness, swelling, and reduced mobility. It significantly impacts the quality of life, particularly among the elderly. Conventional treatment primarily involves non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) and corticosteroids, which, although effective, often lead to adverse effects with long-term use. To address these limitations, the development of a safe, effective, and patient-compliant oral dosage form is essential. Tablets, being the most preferred and convenient form of drug delivery, offer advantages such as accurate dosing, stability, and ease of administration.

Need and Significance of this Research: Arthritis, a leading cause of disability worldwide, affects millions of individuals by impairing joint function and reducing mobility. With the global rise in aging populations and lifestyle-related risk factors, the prevalence of arthritis is steadily increasing. Current treatments, while effective in symptom management, are often associated with adverse effects, high costs, and limited long-term efficacy.

Scope of the Research Work: The scope of this research encompasses the formulation and evaluation

of an anti-arthritis tablet aimed at providing effective and sustained relief from arthritic symptoms. This study includes the selection of suitable active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs) or herbal extracts with proven anti-inflammatory and analgesic properties, along with compatible excipients for optimal tablet performance. The research covers various formulation techniques, optimization of the tablet dosage form, and evaluation based on parameters such as physical characteristics, disintegration time, dissolution rate, drug content uniformity, and stability.

Classification:

1. Non-Steroidal Anti-Inflammatory Drugs (NSAIDs): Examples: Ibuprofen, Diclofenac, And Naproxen
2. Corticosteroids: Examples: Prednisolone, Dexamethasone
3. Disease-Modifying Anti-Rheumatic Drugs (DMARDs): Examples: Methotrexate, Sulfasalazine, and Leflunomide
4. Biologic Agents (Biologic DMARDs): Examples: Infliximab, Etanercept, Adalimumab

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5. Analgesics (Pain Relievers): Examples: Paracetamol (Acetaminophen), Tramadol

7. Nutraceuticals and Supplements: Examples: Glucosamine, Chondroitin, Omega-3 fatty acid.

6. Herbal and Natural Anti-Arthritic Agents: Examples: Turmeric (Curcumin), Boswellia, Ginger,

Figure 1: Effects on the body Rheumatoid arthritis

Etiology:

1. Genetic factor
2. Autoimmune reaction
3. Infection
4. Degeneration and wear and tear
5. Metabolic disorder
6. Joint injury
7. Obesity
8. Environmental and lifestyle factor

Pathophysiology of antiarthritis: The pathophysiology of arthritis varies depending on the type (e.g., osteoarthritis, rheumatoid arthritis), but generally involves inflammation and structural damage to joint components. Below are key mechanisms:

1. Osteoarthritis (OA): Mechanical wear and tear damages articular cartilage over time. Cartilage degradation leads to narrowing of the joint space. Subchondral bone becomes sclerotic, and osteophytes (bone spurs) may form. Synovial inflammation may occur, causing pain and limited movement.

2. Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA): An autoimmune response targets the synovial membrane. Chronic inflammation causes synovial hyperplasia (pannus formation). Pannus invades cartilage and bone, leading to joint destruction. Cytokines like TNF- α and IL-1 play a major role in sustaining inflammation.

3. Gouty Arthritis: Caused by accumulation of uric acid crystals in joints. Crystals trigger an acute inflammatory response, leading to severe pain, redness, and swelling. Common Pathophysiological Features: Inflammation of synovial joints Cartilage degradation and/or bone erosion.

Sign and symptoms:

1. Joint Pain

2. Swelling
3. Stiffness
4. Reduced Range of Motion
5. Redness and Warmth
6. Joint Deformity (in chronic cases)
7. Fatigue and Weakness

DRUG PROFILE

1) ENICOSTEMA AXILLARE

Figure 2: ENICOSTEMA AXILLARE

Classification:

Kingdom: Plantae

Family: Gentianaceae

Genus: Enicostema

Species: E. axillare

Synonym: Enicostema littorale

Biological source: it consist of whole plant parts.

Microscopic characters: a. Colour- greenish b. Odour-characteristic c. Taste- strongly bitter

Phytochemistry:

Chemical formula: C₁₆H₂₂O₁₀

Molecular weight: 374.34g/mol

Structure:

Swertiamarin

Description:

Swertiamarin is a natural compound, a secoiridoid glycoside, found in plants like Enicostemma Axillare (Nai) and Swertia chirata. It's known for its diverse pharmacological properties, including anti-inflammatory, anti-diabetic, and anti-hyperlipidemic effects. It's also been studied for its potential in treating various conditions including arthritis.

Traditional uses:

1) Liver disorders: Traditionally used as a hepatoprotective agent to support liver function and treat jaundice, hepatitis, and other liver ailments.

2) Digestive issues: Used as a bitter tonic to stimulate digestion, appetite, and treat indigestion, flatulence, and constipation.

3) Antipyretic (fever-reducing): Used to lower fever, particularly in conditions like malaria and other febrile illnesses.

Table No: 1 MATERIAL AND SOURCES:

Sr. No.	Name of Material	Sources
1.	Powder extract	Local area of Dharashiv
2.	HPMC	KTPCOP Dharashiv
3.	Guar gum	KTPCOP Dharashiv
4.	Lactose	KTPCOP Dharashiv
5.	PVP K30	KTPCOP Dharashiv
6.	Methyl paraben	KTPCOP Dharashiv
7.	Talc	KTPCOP Dharashiv
8.	Magnesium sterate	KTPCOP Dharashiv

Table No:2 list of Apparatus and instruments:

Sr. No.	Apparatus	Name of company
1.	Soxhlet apparatus	Dolphin
2.	Mortar and pestle	Dolphin
3.	Sieve	Rajesh chemicals
4.	Measuring cylinder	Dolphin
5.	Funnel	Dolphin
6.	Heating mentel	Dolphin
7.	Test tube	Dolphin
8.	Beaker	Dolphin
Instruments		
9.	Weighing balance	Dolphin
10.	Dissolution apparatus	Electrolab
11.	Disintegration apparatus	Dolphin
12.	Friability tester	Roche
13.	U V spectroscopy	Shimadzu
14.	Hardness	Rolex
15.	Thickness	Vernier caliper

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

1. Extraction of *Enicostema axillare*:

Figure 3: Extraction of *Enicostema axillare*

Procedure:

1. Picking, collecting and drying of the whole plant.
2. After that soxhlet extraction take place with 90% methanol for 48hrs.
3. Then extracted material evaporated until it become a solidify by using mortar and pestle in convert in a powder form.
4. Then extracted powder is combine with excipients and form granules.
5. And finally granules are going for the direct compression method.

Table No. 3: Formula for Tablet (Sustained Release):

Ingredient	Quantity for one tablet (250 mg)
Powder extraction	100
HPMC	50
Guar gum	50
Lactose	25
PVP K30	12.5
Methyl paraben	q.s
Talc	10
Magnesium sterate	2.5

Preparation methods of Tablet:

1. Stages involving tablet formulation –
 - a. Preparation of granules
 - b. Mixing of lubricant
 - c. Compression of tablet
 - d. Coating is required
 - e. Evaluation of tablet

Figure 4: Tablet Punching Machine**EVALUATION TEST FOR POWDER:**

1. Colour
2. Odour
3. Taste
4. **Angle of repose:** The angle of repose is an indication of the fractional force existing between the particles. This is the maximum angle possible between the surface of a pile of physical mixture and the horizontal plane. This is given by: $\theta = \tan^{-1} (h/r)$

Figure 5: Angle of repose

Where, θ = angle of repose
 h = height of pile in cm
 r = radius of the pile at the base in cm
 Ans = $\tan^{-1} 22^\circ 47'$

Table No. 4: Angle of repose

Angle of repose	Flow ability
20-30	Good
30-35	Fair
35-40	Poor
> 40	Very poor

5) Bulk density: An accurately weighed quantity of powder, which was previously passed through sieve no 40 and carefully poured into graduated cylinder. Then after pouring the powder into graduated cylinder the powder bed was made uniform without disturbing. Then the volume was measured directly from graduation mark on the cylinder as ml. The volume measure was called as the bulk volume and the bulk density is calculated by using the following formula. Bulk density = weight of powder / volume of packing

6) Tapped density: A quantity of 2 gm of powder from each formula was introduced into a 10 ml measuring cylinder. After an initial volume was observed, the cylinder was allowed to fall under its own weight on hard surface from the height of 2.5 cm at two second intervals. The tapping was continued until no further change in the volume was noted. The tapped density was calculated by using following formula: Tapped density = weight of powder / tapped volume of packing

7) Carr's compressibility index: The Carr's compressibility index was calculated by calculating the tapped and bulk density using the 100 ml measuring cylinder. Compressibility is calculated by the formula: Carr's compressibility index = $(\text{Tapped density} - \text{Bulk density}) / \text{Tapped density} \times 100$

8) Hausner's ratio: Hausner's ratio is a measure of flow ability of a powder, commonly used in pharmaceutical and material sciences. Hausner's ratio = $\text{Tapped density} / \text{Bulk density}$ Ans: 1.15

Evaluation Test for Tablets:

1. Tablet hardness:- The hardness of tablets from all the batches was determined using the Monsanto hardness tester.

2. Friability:- For each formulation, the friability of 20 tablets was determined using the Roche friabilator. In this test tablets were subject to the combined effect of shock and abrasion by utilizing a plastic chamber which revolves at a speed of 25 rpm, dropping the tablets to a distance of 6 inches in each revolution. A sample of pre weighted 20 tablets was placed in Roche friabilator which was then operated for 100 revolutions ie 4 min. Formula = $\frac{\text{initial weight} - \text{final weight}}{\text{initial weight}} \times 100$ Answer = 30

3. Thickness:- Thickness of all tablets was measured using the Vernier caliper.

Figure 6: Thickness measurement

4. Weight variation test:- To study the weight variation, twenty tablets from each formulation were selected at random and determination their average weight. Not more than two of the individual weights may deviate from the average weight by more than the percent deviation and none should deviate by more than twice that percentage.

5. Disintegration Test: Disintegration testing evaluates how quickly and efficiently a tablet or capsule breaks down into smaller fragments in a liquid medium, simulating the conditions.

Figure 7: Disintegration Test

6. Dissolution Test: The dissolution test of tablets performed by the dissolution test apparatus. The tablets are well dissolved in the gastric pH range. This can be observed by U. V. Spectroscopy by using the dissolution method. The tablets are properly dissolved.

Figure 8: Dissolution Test

Figure 9: UV Visible Spectrophotometer

Table No. 5: UV Absorbance:

Sr. No.	Absorbance
1	0.6376
2	1.0726
3	1.2139
4	1.2618
5	1.2806
6	1.3866

EVALUATION TEST FOR EXTRACTION:

Phytochemical Screening:

Alkaloids:

Dragendroff's Test: Drug solution with Dragendroff's reagent (Potassium Bismuth iodide), forms an orange-red color.

Mayer's Test: A drug solution with a few drops of Mayer's reagent (potassium mercuric iodide), forms a creamy white precipitate. **Hager's Test:** Drug solution with a few drops of Hager's reagent (Saturated aq. Solution of Picric acid), forms a crystalline yellow precipitate.

Wagner's Test: Drug solution with a few drops of Wagner's reagent (dilute iodine solution), forms a brown color.

reddish brown precipitate. Tannic Acid Test: Drug solution few drops of the tannic acid solution, formation of a buff-colored precipitate.

Test for Tannins and phenolic compound: 2-3ml of aq. extract and add a few drops of the following reagents 5% FeCl₃ Solutions-Deep blue black colour Lead acetate solution-White ppt Bromine water - Decolourisation of Bromine water Potassium dichromate - red color Dilute Iodine solution - Transient red colour.

Figure 10: Test for Tannins and phenolic compound

THIN LAYER CHROMATOGRAPHY: Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) can be used to identify and quantify swertiamarin. A sample of the compound, either a standard or an extract, is applied to a TLC plate and developed using a suitable solvent system. The resulting spots on the plate are then visualized.

Figure 11: Thin Layer Chromatography

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Formulation of Anti-Arthritis Tablet for Sustained Release by using *Enicostema Axillare* (250 mg): Anti-arthritis tablets were developed using different ratios of active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs), binders, disintegrants, and excipients. The direct compression method was used, and granules were evaluated for flow properties before compression. Pre-compression parameters such as bulk density, tapped density, Carr's index, Hausner's ratio, and angle of repose indicated that the granules had good to excellent flow properties, supporting suitability for tablet compression. Post-compression Evaluation All tablet batches were evaluated for parameters such as: Weight variation: All formulations complied with pharmacopoeial limits.

Hardness: Tablet hardness ranged between 25 – 30 n with showing optimum mechanical strength.

Friability: All formulations had friability below 0.179% indicating good mechanical resistance. Disintegration time: disintegration time of tablet is 13 min, which is within acceptable limits for conventional tablets. Drug content: Uniformity of drug content was observed in all formulations, with values between 97 102%, indicating consistency.

DISCUSSION

Formulation exhibited the best overall performance in terms of physical and chemical evaluation. The selection of disintegrant and binder played a key role in achieving faster disintegration and better dissolution. The results suggest that formulation can be considered a promising formulation for effective anti-arthritis therapy. Moreover, stability studies (if conducted) would further confirm the formulation's shelf life and long term efficacy. The final optimized formulation meets the standard quality parameters, supporting its potential for commercial development.

Figure 12: Antiarthritis Tablet

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The present study successfully formulated and evaluated anti-arthritis tablets using the direct compression method. Among the various formulations, Formulation F9 was found to be the most effective based on its optimal hardness, friability, disintegration time, drug content uniformity. The results indicate that F9 provides a rapid onset of action, making it suitable for effective management of arthritis symptoms. Overall, the findings demonstrate that the selected formulation approach can produce stable, effective, and pharmaceutically acceptable Sustained release anti-arthritis tablets. Further stability testing are recommended to support the clinical efficacy and long-term safety of the developed formulation.

REFERENCES

1. Lachman, L., Lieberman, H. A., & Kanig, J. L. (2009). *The Theory and Practice of Industrial Pharmacy*. 3rd ed., CBS Publishers.
2. Aulton, M. E., & Taylor, K. M. G. (2018). *Aulton's Pharmaceutics: The Design and Manufacture of Medicines*. 5th ed., Elsevier Health Sciences.
3. Indian Pharmacopoeia Commission. (2022). *Indian Pharmacopoeia 2022*. Ghaziabad: Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India.
4. USP-NF. (2021). *United States Pharmacopeia and National Formulary (USP 44-NF 39)*. United States Pharmacopoeial Convention.
5. Sharma, S. K., & Lata, H. (2020). Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Tablets for Arthritis Treatment. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*, 11(4), 1652–1658.
6. Kulkarni, G. T., & Gokhale, R. (2017). Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Tablets for Antiinflammatory Activity. *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics*, 7(7), 109–114.
7. Tripathi, K. D. (2020). *Essentials of Medical Pharmacology*. 8th ed., Jaypee Brothers Medical Publishers.
8. Warrell D.A. Clinical features of Malaria In: Gilles H.M., Warrell D.A., eds. *Bruce-Chawatts Essential Malariology*. 3rd ed. London: Arnold;1993. p. 37–49.
9. Patel D.M., Patel N.M., Pandya N.M., Jogani P.D. Formulation and Optimization of carbamazepine floating tablets. *Indian J Pharm Sci* 2007; 69:763–767.
10. Jaimani M., Rana A.C., Tanwar Y.S. Formulation and evaluation of famotidine floating tablets. *Curr Drug Deliv* 2007;4:51–55.
11. "Formulation and Evaluation of Sustained Release Matrix Tablets of Aceclofenac using Hydroxypropyl Methylcellulose" Published in: *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences (IJPS)*, 2011, Vol 3, Issue 2.
12. Lachman, L., Lieberman, H.A., and Kanig, J.L. *The Theory and Practice of Industrial Pharmacy*, 3rd Edition, Lea & Febiger, 1986. Classic reference for tablet formulation principles.
13. Aulton, M.E. *Aulton's Pharmaceutics: The Design and Manufacture of Medicines*, 4th

- Edition, 2013, Churchill Livingstone. Covers matrix tablets and sustained release formulations.
14. Ansel, H.C., Allen, L.V., and Popovich, N.G. *Pharmaceutical Dosage Forms and Drug Delivery Systems*, 9th Edition, Lippincott Williams & Wilkins. General formulation practices.
 15. Kumar, S., et al. Formulation and Evaluation of Sustained Release Matrix Tablets of Aceclofenac Using Hydroxypropyl Methylcellulose and Carbopol. *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences (IJPSP)*, 2011, Vol 3, Issue 2. Specific for aceclofenac matrix tablets.
 16. Chowdary, K.P.R. and Rao, Y.S. Design and In-vitro Evaluation of Mucoadhesive Sustained Release Tablets of Aceclofenac. *Indian Drugs*, 2003, 40(8), 455-460. Details on antiarthritic SR tablet design.

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